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A Study on Impact of Communication Flow in Channel of Distribution of Lighting LED Industry in Bangalore

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Abstract

Distribution is one of the four essential component of the marketing mix, the other three are product, pricing and promotion. This marketing mix is also discussed and referred as the four Ps of marketing, and ‘distribution’ is here called physical distribution or place. One of the function performed by channel is ‘communication’. The study on marketing channel communication comprises the relationships between: (1) standards of information/communication sharing and communication flows of frequency, bi-directionality, and formality, (2) communication flows to wholesalers, retailer and their assessments of the quality of communication and satisfaction level. And based on data collected with a survey made using appropriate statistical tools, to a sample of lighting dealers, our findings offer insight on channels communication to both researchers and to the corporate decision makers. This is to understand the impact of communication flows on summary judgments of communication. Further managers can channelize and focus on communication flows which stimulate positive outcome of business objectives, and which in turn can stimulate for achieving organisational objective. In general optimal utilization of the scarce of resources such as time and manpower in channel of distribution.

Keywords: Communication, Channel of distribution, Formal communication, Quality of communication.

Introduction

Distribution is one of the four essential component of the marketing mix, the other three are product, pricing and promotion. This marketing mix is also discussed and referred as the four Ps of marketing, and ‘distribution’ is here called physical distribution or place. Since, distribution is the process of delivering the products produced or service offered by a firm to the end user, numerous intermediaries are involved in this channel process. The chain of intermediaries which helps in transferring the product or servicing from one to the next before it reaches the end user is called the ‘Distribution Chain or Distribution Channel’. Each member in the channel of distribution has a specific role and need which the

marketer caters. Some of the major functions performed by the intermediaries are mainly physical distribution, communication and facilitating function. The communication function performed by the channel members is very vital and it can overwhelming impact the relationship among members of the channel, therefore it should managed in appropriate and diligent manner. Here in this research communication not considered as communication mix, which is within the scope of 'Promotion' marketing mix.

Communication activity is a significant, and prime factor in the development of channel relationships and measurement of relationship quality. The general tendency of scholars who tend to take one of two approaches in conceptualizing and defining channel communication: either they focus on the flows of communication between channel members or otherwise they focus on evaluative/summary judgments regarding the communication exchange. Some of them strived to examine on the 'nature of communication flows' stereotypically inspects things like the frequency of interaction, the extent to which communication flows are bidirectional in nature, or the level of formality of communication flows. For instance, Brown (1981) establish the number of communication interactions between channel members over a specified time period, similarly Jakki J Mohr and Ravipreet S Sohi (1995), attempted on quality of communication assessment based on its flow and satisfaction level.

Anderson et al. (1987) reviewed the extent to which both channel members were involved in the give-and-take of communication interactions (i.e., two-way feedback and participation). Anderson and Weitz (1989) highlighted the quantification of expected communication and how they met. Researchers who have focused on summary, evaluative judgments of communication examine the helpfulness (Gultinan, Rejab, and Rodgers, 1980), adequacy (Bialaszewski and Giallourakis, 1985), or efficacy (Anderson and Narus, 1990) of communication flow. Rather than capturing the specific nature of communication flows, such as nature and norms of communication, captured a whole assessment of the quality of communication. This prior research has examined only few aspect of communication flow, without acknowledging the potential for multi-dimensional aspects of communication flows on specific industry and versatile geography such as lighting industry in specific and Bangalore metro in general. If communication is the "glue that holds together the channel of distribution" (Mohr and Nevin, 1990, p.36), it would seem important to include more than one measure of communication flows in channels research. Further, prior research does not acknowledge that the nature of communication flows may form the basis for a channel member's evaluative/summary outcome of communication. For example, the formality with which communication procedures are specified might impact the quality of information distributed among, as well as a channel member's satisfaction with communication. We which examines the impact of communication flows on evaluative/summary judgments of communication would be useful in better managing communication flows.

Therefore, the purpose of this paper is to test the communication flows between manufacturers and dealers. More specifically, we examine four issues:

1. To know rules and procedures of information assimilation and dissemination influence the frequency, bi-directionality, and formality of communication flows;
2. To know these communication flows impact dealers' assessments of the quality of communication;
3. The relationship between communication quality and dealers' level of satisfaction with communication.

In the below sections which follow, we first review the literature on communications in distribution channels. Prior to developing our hypotheses, we establish the theoretical underpinnings of our model. Finally, we discuss our results, interpret and their implications.

The Statement of Problem

The significance of the communication is undeniable, which indeed strategized by the research scholar time and again along with business decision makers. This channel of distribution depends on the glue among the various participants in the order. Hence the quality of communication is assessed on individual participant in channel of distribution on various dimension such as norms of information sharing, frequency, formality, bi-directionally etc. There is also vitality of distribution channel within lighting sector in Bangalore, this could have not done without effective ‘communication’. The focus is on the describing the distribution channel system in such a way that we can adequately capture required evidence on the strategies to be assumed for marketing mix strategies in this said industry for optimising the available resources.

Scope of the Research Work

The study is made within the Bangalore city LED lighting industry primary members of channel of distribution only. This study does not cognize the direct and end consumers perception of quality of communication. Due to distinctiveness and typical nature of lighting LED industry, validation of study lies only on the practical concepts and less rely on theoretical concepts.

This study is not covering the secondary entities such as CFA (clearing and forwarding agents) & CSA (carrying and selling agents) of the lighting led segment in Bangalore city.

Definition of Distribution Channel

Distribution: one of the components of marketing mix that in simplest task transfer the product from the production place to the purchase place to the customer. In other words the main task of distribution management is placing the goods in hand of potential customers at the right time and place (Roosta, A Venus D Ebrahim)

Distribution channels: A collection of affiliate organizations and individuals that place product or services to end customers. Distribution channels connect the good producers and customer to each other. Intermediaries form the components of the distribution channel.

Communication flow identifies the individuals who participate in the flow of information either up or down the channel. It is the one of the important flow in the channel of distribution apart from product flow, negotiation flow, ownership flow, and promotion flow.

Pictorially->

Further to understand the flow of communication, let us understand conceptualize the different dimension of communication (Mohr & Sohi 1995), viz., frequency, bi-directionality and formality. This model so developed to assess the quality of communication flow. The following figure, enumerating the various dimension of the flow of communication.

Figure showing Norms of Information/communication sharing

The above diagram depicts the relationship between the ‘Quality of communications’, mathematically

$$f(Cq)=f, bd, F, \dots$$

Quality of Communication = frequency, bi-directional, Formality.

Objectives of the study

This paper mainly deals on the quality of communication which is resultant said variables. The focal objective of this paper is to test the communication flows between manufacturers and other intermediaries within channel of distribution. More precisely, we prioritize as below:

- To know the role and its efficiency of rules and procedures of information assimilation and dissemination influence the frequency, bi-directionality, and formality of communication flows;
- To know the relationship between communication quality and dealers’ level of satisfaction with communication.
- To know the contemporary channel communication trends in channel of distribution in lighting LED industry in Bangalore.

The below are the hypothesis for the study

1. H0: Norms of information sharing are not positively/negatively related to frequency of communication flow.
H1: Norms of information sharing are positively related to frequency of communication flow.
2. H0: Norms of information sharing are not positively/negatively related to bi-directionality of communication flow.
H1: Norms of information sharing are positively related to bi-directionality of communication flow.

Methodology Adopted

Type of research : Empirical research
 Sampling design : non-probability method
 Data collection tools : questionnaire with 5 point Likert scale

Respondents : intermediaries in lighting LED industry in Bangalore
 Sample size : 25intermediaries (distributor, retailer and dealer)
 Tools employed : Microsoft excel, PearsonCorrelation Co-efficient.

Interpretation and discussion of findings:

The below are the statistical test conducted for H0, and we have used “Pearson Correlation Coefficient” test with variables. It is to understand the how these variable are related to perceived quality of communication.

The first one is on the impact of communication flow on the frequency of information shared among the channel partners. Here, ‘how frequently communication persists among channel members’ via face to face, telephonic etc. the x represents “communication flow” from company to wholesaler and retailer. And Y represents “communication flow” to company from wholesaler and retailer. The 5 point Likert scale, from strongly agree to strongly disagree is being utilized.

x	y	xy	X ²	y ²
7	6	42	49	36
10	12	120	100	144
4	4	16	16	16
3	2	6	9	4
1	0	0	1	0
<u>25</u>	<u>24</u>	<u>184</u>	<u>175</u>	<u>200</u>

$$r = \frac{n(\sum xy) - (\sum x)(\sum y)}{\sqrt{[n(\sum x^2) - (\sum x)^2][n(\sum y^2) - (\sum y)^2]}}$$

$$r = \frac{5(\sum 184) - (\sum 25)(\sum 24)}{\sqrt{[5(\sum 175) - (\sum 25)^2][5(\sum 200) - (\sum 184)^2]}}$$

r = 0.982872, pictorially the trend can be depicted as below in diagram.

Therefore, there exist positive relationship between the frequency communication from company or manufacturer to wholesaler and retailer vis-à-vis wholesaler and retailer to company. Hence H0 is rejected and H1 is accepted.

Second H0 here, the relationship between channel members communication flow on the bi-directionality is assessed. We populate the data on the erstwhile used statistical test used i.e., Pearson Correlation test.

The x represents the ‘feedback given by company to wholesaler and retailer’ in Likert scale from strongly agree to strongly disagree. And the y represents the ‘feedback by retailer wholesaler to company’ with same scale

$$r = \frac{n(\sum xy) - (\sum x)(\sum y)}{\sqrt{[n(\sum x^2) - (\sum x)^2][n(\sum y^2) - (\sum y)^2]}}$$

x	y	xy	x ²	y ²
2	12	24	4	144
8	11	88	64	121
5	0	0	25	0
8	1	8	64	1
2	1	2	4	1
<u>25</u>	<u>25</u>	<u>122</u>	<u>161</u>	<u>267</u>

$$r = \frac{5(122) - (25)(25)}{\sqrt{[5(161) - (25)^2][5(267) - (25)^2]}}$$

$r = -0.04196$

Thus, we can infer from above test & figure is that the flow of communication bi-directional in the lighting industry is negative. Hence we accept the H0 and reject H1.

Directions for Further Research

Greater understanding of channel communication can help focus managerial efforts on vital communication flows which stimulate positive assessments of communication behaviours, and which stymie less beneficial/detrimental communication behaviours. Furthermore, researchers may better understand which dimensions of communication are more appropriate than others for potential inclusion in their theories and research. There are many findings on specified parameter which are challenging but also new boulevards for further validation can be done on other factors. The specified variables can be utilized to assess the communication flow in other industry and sector.

Conclusion

The present work is an attempt to establish, once again, the positive relationship between communication and effectiveness of the channel of distribution. Since the significant change in the communication pattern in the changing channel of distribution in the lighting LED industry, the underlying the fact is that the communication need to bi-directional and more frequent.

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